

Machine Learning on Chronic Kidney Disease Prediction

Using ML method to predict chronic diseases

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ABSTRACT

Chronic kidney disease, also known as Chronic Kidney Disease, is an uncharacteristic function of the kidney or a renal failure that develops over a period of months or years. Usually, chronic kidney disease is diagnosed in screening of people known to be at risk of kidney problems, such as people with high blood pressure or diabetes and People who have a blood relative with Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) patients. Early prediction is therefore necessary to combat the disease of the disease and for good treatment. This study proposes that using machine learning techniques for CKD like Support Vector Machine(SVM) classifier. The final output predicts whether the person has CKD or not by having a minimum number of features. It as per the instructions provided in previous sections. Carry out the steps for Cross-linking and finally, Manuscript validation and placing the respective metadata [1] while applying the required template.

KEYWORDS

Chronic Kidney Disease, SVM, Pre-Processing, Classification

INTRODUCTION

Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) is considered an important one threat to the health of society in today era. Chronic Kidney Disease can be cured by regular laboratory tests will determine and there are some treatments that do prevent development, slow down the progression of the disease, the complications of decreased Glomerular Filtration Rate (GFR) and reduce the risk of cardiovascular disease and survival and die life quality. CKD can be caused dehydration, smoking, poor diet, lack of sleep and diet, lack of sleep and many other factors are caused. This disease affects 753 million people worldwide in 2016, of which 417 million women and 336 million are men. In most cases, the disease recognized only in its final stages and sometimes leads to leads to kidney failure.

The existing diagnostic system is based on the examination of the urine with the help of the serum creatinine value. Many medical methods are used for this purpose, e.g., B. the screening, ultrasonic procedure. During screening, patients are hypertension, cardiovascular disease in the past and patients who have relatives

with kidney disease had kidney disease. This technique involves calculation the estimated GFR from the serum creatinine value and measurement of urinary Albumin-To-Creatinine Ratio (ACR) in a morning urine sample. This paper focuses on Machine Learning technique such as SVM by minimizing the Features and the selection of the best features to ensure the accuracy of to improve prediction. [1][2][3]

METHODS

Dataset

The data set used here is the publicly available CKD Dataset from the Kaggle repository. It contains 400 samples from two different classes. Of the 25 attributes, 11 are numeric and 13 are nominal and one is a class attribute. The record contains Number of missing values. Here the information of the record the patient data such as age, blood pressure, more specific Gravity, Albumin, Sugar, Red Blood Cells, etc.

Table 1 List of attributes present in the CKD Kaggle dataset

Attributes	Type
Age	Numeric
Blood Pressure	Numeric
Specific Gravity	Numeric
Albumin	Numeric
Sugar	Numeric
Red Blood Cells	Nominal
Pus Cell	Nominal
Pus Cell clumps	Nominal
Bacteria	Nominal
Blood Glucose Random	Numeric
Blood Urea	Numeric
Serum Creatinine	Numeric
Sodium	Numeric
Potassium	Numeric
Hemoglobin	Numeric
Packed Cell Volume	Numeric
Red Blood Cell count	Numeric
White Blood Cell Count	Numeric
Hypertension	Nominal
Diabetes Mellitus	Nominal
Coronary Artery Disease	Nominal
Appetite	Nominal
Pedal Edema	Nominal
Anemia	Nominal
Class	Class

Pre-Processing

Data Pre-Processing is that stage where the data that is distorted or encoded is brought to such a state that the machine can easily analyze it. A dataset can be observed as a group of data objects. Data objects are labeled by a number of features, that ensures the basic features of an object, such as the mass of a physical object or the time at which an event ensured. In the dataset there may be missing values, they can either be eliminated or estimated. The most common method of dealing with missing values is filling them in with mean, median or mode value of respective feature. As object values cannot be used for the analysis, we have to convert the numeric values with type as object to float64 type. Null values in the categorical attributes are changed with the most recurrent occurring value current in that attribute column. Label encoding is done to translate categorical attributes into numeric attribute by conveying each unique attribute value to an integer. This automatically changes the attributes to int type. The mean value is premeditated from each column and is used to replace all the missing values in that attribute column. For this function it is using a function called imputer which is used to find the mean value in each column. After the replacing and encoding is done, the data should be trained, validated and tested. Training the data is the part on which our algorithms are actually trained to build a model. Validation is the part of the dataset which is used to validate our various model fits or improve the model. [4][5]

Classification

For classification I use Support Vector Machine (SVM) to predict the disease and its performance. As a first step I must import the libraries for classification and prediction. I import SVM and datasets from the scikit-learn library. NumPy for carrying out efficient mathematical computations. Accuracy-score from sklearn.metrics to predict the accuracy of the model. I have divided the data into training and testing sets. Now is the time to train our SVM on the training data. scikit-learn contains the SVM library, which contains built-in classes for various SVM algorithms. Since I was going to perform a classification task, I will use the support vector classifier class, which is written as SVC in the scikit-learn SVM library. This class takes one parameter, which is the kernel form. The fit method of SVC class is called to train the algorithm on the training data, which is passed as a parameter to the fit method. To make predictions, the predict method of the SVC class is used. For evaluating the algorithm, I use the confusion matrix. [3][4]

Support Vector Machine

In machine learning, Support Vector Machine (SVM) are supervised learning models with related learning algorithms that examine data used for classification and regression analysis. Given a set of training examples, each marked as belonging to one or the other of two categories, an SVM training algorithm builds a model that assigns new examples to one category or the other, making it a nonprobabilistic binary linear classifier. SVM works by mapping data to a high-dimensional feature space so that data

points can be classified, even when the data are not otherwise linearly separable. [3]

DISCUSSION

The metrics provided below gives information on the quality of the outcomes that I get in this study. A confusion matrix helps with this by describing the performance of the classifier.

Table 2 Confusion Matrix

Confusion Matrix	CKD (Predicted)	Not CKD (Predicted)
CKD (Actual)	TP	FN
Not CKD (Actual)	FP	TN

Precision: Precision or positive predictive value here is the ratio of all patients with CKD to all the patients predicted with CKD (true positive and false positive).

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

Recall: It is also known as sensitivity, and it is the ratio of actual number of CKD patients that are correctly identified to the total no of patients with CKD.

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

F- Measure: It measures the accuracy of the test. It is the harmonic mean between precision and recall.

$$\text{F-Measure} = 2 * \frac{\text{Recall} * \text{Precision}}{\text{Recall} + \text{Precision}}$$

Accuracy: It is the ratio of correctly predicted output cases to all the cases present in the data set.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FP + TN + FN}$$

Support: Support is the correct number of outcomes or responses that are present in each class of the predicted outcome.

Table 3 Results of CKD prediction using SVM

	PRECISION	RECALL	F1-SCORE	SUPPORT
CKD	1.00	0.94	0.97	83
Not CKD	0.88	1.00	0.94	37
Accuracy			0.96	120
Macro-Average	0.94	0.97	0.95	120
Weighted Average	0.96	0.96	0.96	120

CONCLUSION

This paper deals with the prediction of CKD in people. In this classification problem SVM classifies the output into two class with CKD and without CKD. The main objective of this study was to predict patients with CKD using less number attributes while maintaining a higher accuracy. Here I obtain an accuracy of about 96 percentage.

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